

Figure 5b: The 9x9 vāstu, BS 52.42-50.

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|-----------------|------------------------|----------------|
| 1 Brahmā | 19 Viṣṇu (Satya) | 37 Pāpayakṣman |
| 2 Aryaman | 20 Bhṛṣa | 38 Roga |
| 3 Vivasvant | 21 Antarikṣa | 39 Ahi |
| 4 Mitra | 22 Vāyu | 40 Mukhya |
| 5 Pṛthivīdhara | 23 Pūṣan | 41 Bhallāṭa |
| 6 Āpa | 24 Vitatha | 42 Soma |
| 7 Āpavatsa | 25 Bṛhatkṣata | 43 Bhujaga |
| 8 Savitr | 26 Yama | 44 Aditi |
| 9 Sāvitr | 27 Gandharva | 45 Diti |
| 10 Indra | 28 Bhṛṅga | |
| 11 Indrajit | 29 Mṛga | |
| 12 Rudra | 30 Pitṛ | |
| 13 Rājayakṣman | 31 Dauvārika | |
| 14 Śikhi (Agni) | 32 Sugrīva | |
| 15 Parjanya | 33 Kusumadanta | |
| 16 Jayanta | 34 Ambupati (Pracetas) | |
| 17 Mahendra | 35 Asura | |
| 18 Sūrya | 36 Śoṣa | |

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38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	14
37	12						6	15
36		13	5			7	16	
35			1			2	17	
34		4					18	
33							19	
32		10	2			8	20	
31	11						9	21
30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22